

High Resolution Time Difference of Arrival Using Timestamps for Localization in 802.11b/g Wireless Networks

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Abstract—Localization of mobile devices is an area of much interest in both the commercial, and government sectors. One particular method of localization uses time-difference of arrival (TDoA) measurements from multiple receivers. This can be done using shared timestamps indicating the time of arrival (ToA) among distributed receivers. High resolution timestamps are particularly important to ensure reasonable spatial resolution of the localization method. This paper presents a method to obtain high-resolution time-of-arrival stamps for 802.11b frames based on matched filtering and time-averaged power. This method can be extended to the higher data rates used by 802.11g.

I. INTRODUCTION

The area of localization in wireless networks has been growing rapidly, with rising interest in location-aware applications in mobile devices such as cell phones, PDA's and laptops. Localization of nodes within a wireless network has many potential applications, both within the commercial marketplace, and in government.

The use of timestamps for localization has received a good deal of attention recently. The primary advantage of using timestamps is they it allows distributed systems to perform the measurements, rather than relying on a centralized system to perform a cross-correlation on all the received signals.

This paper present a specific mechanism for obtaining high resolution timestamps for measuring the time of arrival (ToA) of an 802.11b signal. In addition, this technique could easily be extended to the higher data rates used in 802.11g. This method relies on detecting the time-of-arrival of the preamble in the wider-bandwidth, spread-spectrum signal, rather than on the de-spread signal and its resulting bit stream. For compatibility with older radios, the preamble of 802.11b and 802.11g is sent at the 1 or 2Mbps data rate using the direct sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) physical layer specification [7]. This allows the distributed coordination function (DCF) to function for older radios which don't support the higher data rates. In addition, beacon frames, which advertise accessible access points, are typically sent at the 1Mbps data rate at regular intervals. The DSSS nature of the preamble is leveraged by the method presented, and allows the technique to be extended to the higher data used in the 802.11g standard.

This mechanism is suitable for use in performing localization either by measuring the time-difference of arrival (TDoA),

or for obtaining ranging estimates directly via time of flight (ToF) estimation. Typically the time-difference is estimated by performing a form of cross-correlation on the received baseband signals [1], [2], [3]. However, this requires a high-bandwidth link capable of transmitting the baseband samples from each receiver back to a central processor to perform the cross-correlation. Techniques relying on receivers transmitting a timestamp back to a central processor, or among the nodes in a wireless network have been demonstrated [4]. However commercially available 802.11 chipsets, as available in many adapters such as the AirPcap from CACE Technologies [5] typically provide a timestamp resolution of $1\mu s$, which corresponds to the data rate of the transmitted bits in the preamble (1Mbps). This in turn translates into a spatial resolution of approximately 300m when used for ToA based ranging. The error in localization based on TDoA measurements is likely much greater due to the hyperbolic geometry of the equations used [6].

Voltz and Hernandez [8] explored using a maximum likelihood estimator of time of arrival for use in OFDM signals in a multipath environment. Their work was primarily concerned with identifying the line of sight (LOS) signal in an unknown multi-path channel.

Ciurana, Barcelo-Arroyo and Izquierdo [9] use a 44MHz clock to obtain a resolution of 22ns in round-trip time (RTT) measurements to obtain ranging information. The system they described used 300 measurements in order to estimate the true RTT between two nodes. However, the exact nature of the time of arrival estimator is not described.

Wang, Lu and Chen [10] similarly relied on a receiver capable of high-resolution timestamps to measure propagation time for ranging and localization, but they do not address how this ns -level resolution will be obtained.

The use of matched filtering to obtain high resolution timestamps was also discussed by Golden and Bateman [11] for time of arrival based ranging, in the context of a complete system for performing TOA based localization of client nodes. Their results did not report the resolution of their time of arrival estimator, however they did show a root mean square error (RMSE) of approximately 0.4m in a cabled environment with averaging over 200 measurements. This roughly corre-

Fig. 1: Block diagram of an 802.11b receiver

sponds to a resolution of 1.3ns, but we do not know how well it performs with fewer available measurements, and the mechanism used to obtain the timestamps is not thoroughly described.

In addition, Li, Pahlavan, Latva-Aho, and Ylianttila [12] evaluated the theoretical applicability of using pseudo-noise (PN) code acquisition and synchronization techniques for high resolution time delay measurements in TDoA-based localization. They were able to report a synchronization error probability density function with most of the errors residing in less than 20ns for DSSS by up-sampling at the receiver by 9 (i.e. sampling at 99Mhz) in an AWGN noise channel for low SNR conditions.

This paper investigates implementing a PN-code matched filter scheme for obtaining high resolution timestamps for use in localization via TDoA with a software radio on a general purpose processor, and offers some discussion on integration with the rest of the receiver blocks.

Testing was done with MATLAB, as well as with the GNURadio [13] software-defined radio framework, which uses general purpose processors (GPPs), and runs on a variety of operating systems.

II. METHODOLOGY

The method introduced is based on matched filtering, similar to PN-code acquisition via a correlator structure. A matched filter is constructed for the Barker 11-chip sequence as used in the IEEE 802.11-2007 standard [7]. Any DSSS signal using this Barker sequence—such as the preamble in the 802.11b/g standards, as well as for the rest of the frame at the lowest data rates (1 and 2Mbps)—will appear as a train of DPSK modulated pulses (DBSPK for 1Mbps, and DQPSK for 2Mbps). The objective is to determine the exact starting position of this train of pulses, in the presence of noise, which will be referred to as the timestamp.

A block diagram of a typical 802.11-type radio is shown in Fig. 1. The RF front end is responsible for tuning to the appropriate channel in the 2.4GHz band and converting the RF signal into baseband for the rest of the processing blocks. The de-spreading block is responsible for correlating the received signal with the Barker 11-chip sequence, reducing the signal to the original DBPSK or DQPSK modulated 1MS/s signal. The bits must then be descrambled. The de-framer looks for a valid Physical Layer Convergence Protocol (PLCP) header (Fig. 2).

The block diagram of the method described is shown in Fig. 3. The portion within the box label BBN is based on the code provided by the BBN ADROIT [14] project, and consists of a de-spreading block using the Barker 11-chip matched

Fig. 2: PLCP frame format, from [7]

Fig. 3: Block diagram of proposed method

filter, and a symbol synchronizer which is based on a peak finder. The added blocks from the proposed algorithm consist of the time-averaged power block, differentiator, threshold detector, and a peak finder.

The main problem as stated is determining, reliably, the start of the pulse train from the 128 sync bits in the PLCP frame, in noise. The method presented will rely on two techniques: the time-averaged power—specifically the slope of the time-averaged power—and a peak finder to reliably locate a specific point relative to the start of a transmitted frame. The slope of the time-averaged power enables a gross measurement of the start of the frame, similar to a PN-chip acquisition method. The peak finder provides the finer-grained measurement analogous to the PN-chip tracking. The formula used for time-averaged power is shown in (1) over multiple bit periods in discrete time, where s is the discrete time signal, m is the bit period in samples, and n is the number of bit periods over which to average. Note this representation requires knowledge of samples from the future—in a real-time system this would be re-written using samples from the past. The slope of the time-averaged power is then computed as shown in 2, where the instantaneous slope is found simply through the difference between successive samples.

$$P_a[k] = \frac{\sum_{i=k}^{k+(n \cdot m)} |s[i]|^2}{n \cdot m} \quad (1)$$

$$Slope[k] = \frac{\Delta P_a[k]}{\Delta k} = P_a[k] - P_a[k - 1] \quad (2)$$

The start of the 802.11 waveform used in this paper is shown in Fig. 4. As seen in Fig. 4(c) the time-average power (computed over three chip-periods, $3\mu s$, to reduce variation)

Fig. 4: (a) 802.11 waveform with 100 microseconds of delay (b) Signal with matched filter applied (c) Magnitude of matched filtered signal and time-averaged power

will undergo steep changes with the arrival of each pulse in the train. The delay in the arrival of the pulses in the matched filtered signal compared to the original signal can also be seen. As this delay is fixed, and shared by all the receivers, it has no effect on the computed TDoA.

Examples of the same 802.11 waveform in an additive, white, Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel are shown in Fig. 5 and 6 with 5dB signal to noise ratio (SNR). Fig. 6 shows the instantaneous slope of the time-averaged power (red) overlaid the matched filtered signal (green, blue) as received at the two different simulated receivers. The second receiver (b) has an additional $1.2\mu\text{s}$ of delay introduced, simulating a range difference of approximately 350m. Black lines show the time of arrival as found by the algorithm presented. Time of arrival resolution is based on the sampling rate at the output of the matched filter.

By simple differentiation over each successive sample, the slope of the time-average power can be found. As seen in Fig. 6, this corresponds well to the arrival times of the incoming pulses. The algorithm waits for the slope of the average power to exceed a set threshold, and then uses a simple peak-finding method to determine the timestamp. Using the slope of the time-averaged power was observed to be less prone to error, and required less adjustments to the threshold used than searching for the initial peak from the raw output of the matched filter.

Because the presence of a valid 802.11 frame cannot be determined until the de-framing block, which operates on the much lower data rate of extracted bits, the timestamp must be maintained until the de-framing block has determined the presence, or absence of an 802.11 frame. In a synchronous operation, this is straightforward, however in the case of a software radio operating on a general purpose processor (GPP), with each block operating asynchronously (e.g. via sep-

Fig. 5: (a) 802.11 waveform with 100 microseconds of delay in AWGN channel (b) Signal with matched filter applied (c) Magnitude of matched filtered signal and time-averaged power

Fig. 6: (a) Magnitude of matched filter output, and slope of time-averaged power at first receiver. (b) Magnitude of matched filter output, and slope of time-averaged power at second receiver.

arate threads, possibly on different cores), this requires some synchronization mechanism between the timestamp block, and the de-framing block. For simplicity, the method presented only saves the valid timestamp for at least the duration of the train of pulses, as determined by the time-averaged power calculation. When the average power drops back below a set threshold, the timestamp block will begin searching for the start of the next frame. It is assumed that de-framing block is able to determine the presence of a valid 802.11 frame in the period between the timestamp is determined and the start of the next frame. The results in this paper are based on sampled data (and in the case of Matlab, simulated data) consisting of complex samples, with in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) components, at 25MS/s. This provides at best a resolution of

Fig. 7: Block diagram of simulated system

40ns for the resulting timestamps. While this is a significant improvement on the 1 microsecond resolution available from most 802.11 adapters, it is believed this method can be further improved through higher sampling rates.

III. RESULTS

Testing of the algorithm was done with a simulated transmission of an 802.11-compliant, DSSS DBPSK frame, using code based on what was written by BBN [14], and currently hosted and maintained on CGRAN [15], a repository of third-party code for use with GNUradio. The simulated transmission is passed through two channels (Fig. 7)—simulating two spatially separated receivers—which introduce a delay, and noise. For these tests, a SNR of 5db was used.

As the goal of this work is to perform localization via TDoA measurements, the results of primary interest are the effects ToA error has on the TDoA error. The relationship between error in the ToA timestamp and error in the subsequently calculated TDoA measurement is shown in (3) and (4), where ToA_{true} is the time of arrival at the first receiver, and ToA_{btrue} is the time of arrival at the second receiver.

$$err_{ToA} = ToA_{true} - ToA_{est} \quad (3)$$

$$err_{TDoA} = TDoA_{true} - TDoA_{est} \quad (4)$$

$$= (ToA_{true} - ToA_{btrue}) - (ToA_{est} - ToA_{best})$$

Fig. 8 shows a histogram of TDoA error in the simulated environment (AWGN with 5dB SNR) over 1000 trials. It can be seen that although the error distribution is primarily centered about zero, two distinct peaks are present at $\pm 1\mu s$. This can be explained by the detector 'missing' the first peak, from the initial symbol being transmitter. As the symbol rate in the preamble of 802.11 frames is 1Mbps, the matched filter output has peaks every $1\mu s$. A more quantitative measure of the error distribution can be gained by taking the root mean square (RMS) error in (5), which provides a good measure of accuracy in an estimator. The computed RMS error can be found in Table I.

$$err_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n err_{TDoA_i}^2} \quad (5)$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{err_{TDoA_1}^2 + err_{TDoA_2}^2 + \dots + err_{TDoA_n}^2}{n}}$$

TDoA measurements can be treated as a random variable [9], and a statistical estimator based on multiple samples can be used to improve performance. By keeping track of the

Fig. 8: Histogram of error in TDoA estimates using a single measurement

Fig. 9: Histogram of error in TDoA estimates with moving average of five measurements

TDoA vector for each source Media Access Control (MAC) address which has been received, a simple moving average filter can be applied over multiple observations, greatly improving results. Source MAC address spoofing would be a concern in this case, but is outside the scope of this paper. Fig. 9 shows a histogram of TDoA error with a moving average of five measurements. As can be seen both the percentage of errors near $1\mu s$ and the RMS error has been reduced, but the effects of averaging has changed the 'spread' the distribution of error about zero. The results of using a median averaging method, rather than the mean are shown in Fig. 10. The histogram shows an improvement over using a single measurement, without the change in 'spread' as with the moving average. This improvement is also reflecting in the smaller RMS error shown in Table I.

Fig. 10: Histogram of error in TDoA estimates with median averaging over five measurements

Averaging of TDoA Measurements	RMS Error (s)
None	2.5833e-07 (s)
Mean of 5 Measurements	1.9523e-07 (s)
Median of 5 Measurements	1.5781e-07 (s)

TABLE I: TDoA Estimate RMS Error

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented results of using the slope of the time-averaged power output from a matched filter to detect the ToA of an 802.11b frame. This is a low-complexity mechanism for obtaining high-resolution timestamps for received DSSS 802.11b packets, and is able to operate on a 25Msamples/s data rate. Additional processing, such as moving average, or median filtering can greatly increase the accuracy of the resulting TDoA estimates. The ToA from multiple receivers was used to compute the TDoA, which can then be used to localize the source of the transmissions via a distributed set of receivers. Results from using several averaging techniques with multiple ToA measurements from the same MAC address to estimate the true TDoA were also shown. Note that this is only a single component of a complete TDoA- or ToA-based localization system, and while the accuracy of a complete system will depend on a variety of factors not addressed here (i.e. number and location of receivers, the environment in which the system is used, what additional statistical processing is applied to the ToA measurements, etc.), it is the belief of the author that any improvements in localization systems that are applied to 802.11-type networks require a high-resolution timestamp, such as that obtained by the described mechanism.

Li, et al. [12] found that the probability distribution function of synchronization errors for DSSS signals using lies primarily in the tens of nanoseconds (<50ns). However, in applying the technique to detecting the time of arrival of an 802.11b frame, a large source of error results from when the receiver is unable to distinguish the initial peak output by the matched filter

from the noise. This means the technique is very sensitive to the threshold chosen, and the noise environment. In particular, in indoor or urban environments, where the LOS signal may be greatly reduced due to obstacles, detecting the earliest arrival is of particular importance in order to reduce error in the estimate. These incidences of large error can have a large impact on the distribution of error when averaging over multiple measurements to estimate the time-of-arrival from a signal source (e.g. via source MAC address).

V. FUTURE WORK

This method of obtaining high-resolution timestamps appears very promising, and bears further investigation into the real-world applicability. In particular, it would be useful to investigate the performance of the algorithm in both indoor and outdoor environments. Some initial testing using the USRP2 and GNUradio in indoor settings have shown promising results, but more rigorous, controlled testing is required. It should also be a simple matter to extend the algorithm to support the higher data rates as specified in the IEEE 802.11g standard [7]. As the preamble in the higher data rates preserves the DSSS nature of the lower data rates, the timestamp algorithm should continue to function unmodified.

Further improvements in the estimator should be investigated. If the case where the ToA is off by a full symbol period (1μs) can be detected, and either corrected or discarded, the error in the TDoA measurements can be greatly improved.

Another avenue of investigation involves replacing the manual setting of the threshold used in this paper with an adaptive technique that is robust to changing noise environments.

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